

DEMONSTRATION OF THE SOCIAL FUNCTION OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN**Khalilov M.***Associate Professor, Tashkent State University of Economics***Abstract**

This article explains the essence of social entrepreneurship and its important place in our society. Entrepreneurship is important in the economy and social life of the country, on the one hand, it produces goods and services for the population of the country, on the other hand, it contributes to the employment of the population. In the study, business entities serve to solve issues important to society, i.e., social problems, and their social function is important for society, and recommendations are made for strengthening and developing attention to this social function.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, social function, employment, standard of living, welfare.

Introduction

The experience of countries around the world shows that the use of the social function of entrepreneurship in positively solving social problems and improving the well-being of the population leads to positive results. In particular, the implementation of the social function of entrepreneurship in providing employment to the unemployed, increasing the income of the population, improving working conditions, solving the problem of poverty, and developing the infrastructure of the region increases the possibility of effectively solving social problems in society.

Uzbekistan is experiencing a period of changes and developments in line with the countries of the world, the social, economic, and political consciousness of the population has changed, a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship has been formed and widespread attention is being paid to it. The high importance of entrepreneurship in the country's economy has become an axiom. In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, based on the principle of "State for Man", social tasks such as "development of entrepreneurship in neighborhoods, ensuring employment and reducing poverty" have been identified. In fulfilling these tasks, one of the important directions is the effective use of the social function of entrepreneurship and small business entities.

Theoretical aspects of research.

The theoretical and methodological foundations and theoretical aspects of entrepreneurship, the development of small business, its state regulation, and the improvement of economic mechanisms have been thoroughly analyzed in the scientific works of foreign scholars A. Smith, J.B. Say, R. Cantillon, and Y. Schumpeter [1,2,3].

General aspects of the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan are described in the works of Yo. Abdullayev, M.R. Boltabayev and other scientists [4,5]. Ways to increase the efficiency of small business activities in economic sectors and socio-economic problems of its development are considered in the scientific research of H.P. Abulqosimov [6]. Issues of modeling and forecasting the development trends of small business and entrepreneurship are considered in the research of B. Yu. Khodiyev [7]. Also, U.V. Gafurov [8], in his research, paid attention to the issues of improving state support for the activities of small business and private entrepreneurship entities.

Methodological aspects of research.

This research used statistical scientific abstraction, empirical and economic analysis methods to study the development of entrepreneurship and small business. Based on the analysis and synthesis of data, conclusions and proposals were developed on the development of the social function of entrepreneurship.

Analysis and Results

When we dwell on the essence of the social function, it is easy to first bring to mind the social functions of the state, clarifying the directions of the social functions of entrepreneurship. The social tasks of the state are multifaceted in their content. The most important of them are to employ able-bodied people, to provide social protection to those who need the support of the state, and to create equal opportunities for a prosperous life for all people.

Also, the social functions of the state include education, science, culture, and the protection of citizens' health. This function occupies an important place in the system of internal functions of the state. The state's desire to build a social legal society leads to the enrichment of the social function with new content.

One of the specific features of the social function of entrepreneurship is that the benefits it brings to society are immeasurable. For example, social assistance provided to employees, a healthy working environment, environmental cleanliness in the area where it operates, a reduction in theft and other types of crime, etc. Taking these into account is not only difficult, but also controversial.

When implementing its social policy, a legal state must allocate the necessary funds for healthcare, cultural recreation, education, construction, transport and communication, and it is important that every citizen has access to them.

For example, after the global financial crisis in 2008, a form of restructuring investment called "impact investment" emerged. One of its main goals, in addition to profit, is to have a positive impact on the social sphere and the environment.

The "impact investment" market was worth \$50 billion in 2009, and by 2019 its volume had reached \$502 billion. Such growth reflects the growing attention and goodwill of business towards social and environmental issues.

Today, all social issues, including public health, physical culture and sports, environmental and sanitary-epidemiological programs, are mainly financed by

the state, which is certainly commendable. However, the epidemiological crisis “Covid 2020” that occurred in 2020 made the need for a new approach to this issue an urgent issue. That is, it showed that it is appropriate for the state to transfer certain social functions to other economic entities.

The funds allocated by the state to the social sphere in 2025 will account for 52 percent of state budget expenditures, or 178 trillion sums. 3 trillion 480

billion sums are allocated for ecological and environmental protection measures¹.

The assumption of a certain part of the state's social functions by business entities allows the state to spend financial resources more efficiently, as well as to finance other social areas and programs. Based on an in-depth study of entrepreneurship, we believe that it is appropriate to transfer some of the state's social functions to other entities, including business (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The transfer of social functions of the state to business entities and the evolution of social entrepreneurship²

The social sphere, the social function of entrepreneurship, is of great importance in our country, because it is the main criterion of the people's lifestyle. Previously, the concept of poverty was alien to us, but today it has become one of the main problems that the state needs to solve. We do not make a sharp distinction between traditional entrepreneurship, which is mainly focused on profit, and an entrepreneur who focuses more on social issues, because both of them perform social functions by creating new jobs and paying reasonable wages to workers. The distinctive features of entrepreneurs who pay more attention to social issues, in particular, to the social function, are that they combine economic (profit through the production of goods and services), social (creating new jobs, paying reasonable wages, etc.) and environmental (efficient use of resources, compliance with environmental regulations). From this we can conclude that an entrepreneur creates both economic and social value at the same time.

The social functions of entrepreneurship embody a new approach to existing issues. Every country has many social problems, such as: unemployment, poverty, a decrease in the number of free services, a decrease in the standard of living, etc. The state's support

for entrepreneurship, taking into account its social functions, allows it to change these social problems in a positive direction. Small business and private entrepreneurship, although they do not have sufficient experience in this area, have great potential.

Entrepreneurship, especially entrepreneurship that is oriented towards positive change and solution of social issues, is necessary for the continuous development of the country, because it can contribute to economic development based on innovative approaches and effectively use previously unused resources. Such entrepreneurs are shown as individuals who are ready to take investment risks in order to implement their ideas and expand their activities.

The entrepreneur's adherence to social principles and the fulfillment of social functions depends on two important factors. These factors are manifested, firstly, in the profit of the entrepreneur, and secondly, in the presence and implementation of a social goal. Their mutual balance determines the essence of the social function of entrepreneurship, on the basis of which the characteristics of the social activity of entrepreneurship are formed (Figure 2).

¹ <https://uz24.uz/uz/articles/byudjet-24-12-3>

² Prepared by the author.

Figure 2. Manifestation of signs of social function in entrepreneurial activity³

The social function of entrepreneurship should be reflected in the life idea of all entrepreneurs and business entities. The reason is that the social function of entrepreneurship embodies the self-awareness, image formation, innovation and striving for goals of the Uzbek entrepreneur. Entrepreneurs in the same direction can put forward new models of development in the “New Uzbekistan”.

Conclusion

A business entity is responsible to the community and society in which it operates. This requires the entrepreneur to spend a certain amount of the income and profit earned as a result of the products or activities he produces, either directly by the entrepreneur himself or through social assistance funds for the welfare and well-being of society, in the form of wages, taxes, and donations.

As a practical result of the social function of entrepreneurship, a new social group of entrepreneurs is formed, middle-class owners, that is, economically well-off people in society, appear, and as a result of paying reasonable salaries to workers and employees and providing comfortable working conditions, people's negative attitude towards business and entrepreneurs is changed to a positive one.

One of the distinctive features of the social function of entrepreneurship is that the benefits it brings to society are immeasurable. For example, social assistance provided to its employees, a healthy working environment, a reduction in theft and other types of

crimes in the area where it operates, and a cleaner environment.

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³ Prepared by the author.